

The Use of Differential Methods and their TSE Impacts on the 2022 National Household Travel Survey¹

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Abstract

The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) of the U.S. Department of Transportation periodically conducts the National Household Travel Survey (NHTS), which is considered to be the authoritative source on the travel behavior of the American public. It is the only source of national data that enables the analysis of trends in personal and household travel. It includes daily non-commercial travel by all modes, including characteristics of the people traveling, their household, and their vehicle(s).

For the NHTS that was conducted in 2022, FHWA used two different survey sampling, recruitment, data collection, and weighting designs: (1) an address-based sample (ABS) design and (2) a panel frame sample (PFS) design. For 2022, the data collected via the ABS design are the “official” data for this survey, while the data collected via the PFS design were gathered and evaluated to determine if the PFS design could eventually replace the ABS design in future instances of the NHTS. To support that effort, FHWA contracted for an independent assessment of the comparability of these two survey designs in terms of their sampling and recruitment methodologies, data quality, and weighting.

This manuscript presents information that details the independent assessment that was conducted. The evaluation was guided by the Total Survey Error framework. Among the hundreds of comparisons made between the corresponding findings of the 2022 ABS and PFS surveys, very few meaningfully statistically significant differences in core attributes were found. These differences primarily pertained to demographic attributes, not to travel-related attributes.

Key Words: Total Survey Error (TSE), National Household Travel Survey (NHTS), Fit for Purpose (FFP)

1. Introduction

This manuscript presents the findings from a survey-vs-survey evaluation of the two separate surveys that were used to gather data using the 2022 National Household Travel Survey (NHTS) questionnaire. The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) has conducted the NHTS every 5 to 8 years since 1969 (originally, it was known as the National Personal Travel Survey).

In 2022, one NHTS survey used an addressed-based sampling (ABS) design and the other NHTS survey used a panel frame sampling (PFS) design to each gather more than 7,400 completed questionnaires. The two surveys were conducted simultaneously by the same survey contractor.

¹ The views and opinions expressed in this manuscript are the authors’ and do not necessarily reflect those of FHWA or the U.S. Department of Transportation (USDOT). The contents do not necessarily reflect the official policy of the USDOT.

In comparing the findings of the two 2022 NHTS surveys with each other, among the hundreds of statistical comparisons that were carried out, very few meaningfully statistically significant differences in core attributes were found between the two surveys. And, the majority of these differences pertained to demographic attributes, not travel-related attributes. Thus, the two surveys, as designed and implemented, basically led to the same conclusions regarding the core attributes measured by the NHTS 2022 questionnaire. Furthermore, both the 2022 ABS NHTS and 2022 PFS NHTS were judged to be “Fit for Purpose” (cf. Santos, 2014).

This manuscript presents information that details the independent assessment that was conducted. The evaluation was guided by the Total Survey Error framework (Biemer, 2010; Groves, 1989; Groves et al., 2009; Lavrakas, 2013).

2. Methods

The target population of the 2022 NHTS studies was all non-institutionalized residents of the United States aged 5 and older. The data collection field period for both 2022 surveys was for 365 consecutive days between late January 2022 and late January 2023. One adult per household was selected by the household as the designated respondent for the household. Other residents of the household, aged 16 and older, were asked to complete a person-level questionnaire about their travel-day. (All household members aged 5-15 had personal-level travel day data provided by an adult proxy in the household).

2.1 2022 NHTS ABS Design

The ABS design used a sampling frame composed of the United States Postal Service’s Computerized Delivery Sequence File, which was enhanced by the survey contractor’s sampling vendor to provide more than 98% coverage of the NHTS target population. A geographically stratified sample of 72,288 addresses in the 50 states and the District of Columbia was drawn from the frame. Recruitment was carried out via mailings to the initial sample addresses. The estimated AAPOR RR3 response rate was 12%. The estimated AAPOR COOP (cooperation) rate was 13%. Using the 2022 NHTS questionnaires, more than 99% of the completions were gathered via computer-assisted web interviewing (CAWI) software, with less than 1% gathered via a respondent-requested paper mail-back questionnaire. The final national 2022 ABS sample size of completions was 7,893.

2.2 2022 NHTS PFS Design

The PFS design used a sampling frame composed of all panelists in the survey contractor’s very large national U.S. panel, which was originally established in the late 1990s by another company. The extent of the coverage of this panel of the NHTS’s target population is unknown for various historical reasons. An initial sample of 18,161 panelists in the 50 states and the District of Columbia was drawn from the panel frame using probability proportional to size (PPS) sampling. Recruitment was carried out via emails sent to the initial sample panelists. The estimated cumulative AAPOR RR3 response rate was 2%. The estimated AAPOR COOP rate was 42%. All of the completions were gathered via CAWI software. The final national 2022 PFS sample size of completions was 7,468.

2.3 Use of the TSE Framework

As described throughout this manuscript, the Total Survey Error (TSE) framework was used to organize/guide the comparative evaluation. (See Figure 1 for a schematic of the TSE framework.)

Information was sought by the evaluation team from FHWA and the survey contractor about the following aspects of each 2022 NHTS surveys: (1) coverage and coverage error, (2) sampling and sampling error, (3) nonresponse and nonresponse error, (4) adjustment and adjustment error, (5) measurement and measurement error, and (6) processing and processing error. The vast majority of the information that was requested from FHWA and the survey contractor was provided; however, not all requested information was available (e.g., auxiliary data about person-level, household-level,

and local block-group-level characteristics of the initially sampled ABS addresses and initially sampled PFS panelists; past PFS panel performance paradata about the initially sampled panelists were not available).

Figure 1: The Total Survey Error Framework (Adapted from Groves et al., 2009)

2.4 Primary Goals of the Evaluation

The primary goals of this project were to (1) gather and use information about the methodological aspects of each of the two 2022 NHTS studies in order to identify nonignorable differences between the research methods and statistical procedures used to conduct each study, (2) determine if there were meaningful statistically significant differences between each of the core attributes that the surveys measured, and (3) determine whether those design differences were likely to be related to (i.e., help to explain) the meaningfully significant differences that were observed in the core attributes gathered in both studies. The goals were pursued as follows.

2.4.1 Identify the Differential Methods used in the 2022 NHTS surveys

This goal focused on gathering accurate and detailed information about differences between the methods and statistical procedures used to conduct the two 2022 NHTS surveys. To carry out this goal, the team requested myriad detailed information from the survey contractor and FHWA about each survey's respective (1) frames and coverage (including gaining access to noncoverage-related paradata for each survey), (2) sampling design and execution, (3) recruitment and nonresponse (including gaining access to other nonresponse-related paradata for each survey), (4) weighting/adjustments, (5) questionnaire(s) and modes of data collection, and (6) data processing.

2.4.2 Identify Nonignorable Differences in Core Attributes between the 2022 NHTS Surveys

This goal focused on conducting reliable statistical analyses to determine if any core attribute measured in each survey differed to a meaningful statistically significant extent. The latter meant that size of the observed difference between the two surveys must be at least five percent in absolute size and must be significant at the $p < .05$ level. To carry out this goal, the team performed a variety of statistical analyses including z-tests, Chi-square tests, correlation tests, and regressions.

2.4.3 Identify Possible TSE Causes of the Meaningful Differences in Findings between the 2022 NHTS surveys

This goal focused on analyzing the core attributes in the final 2022 NHTS datasets to identify possible TSE-related issues that might explain the observed nonignorable differences between the core attributes of the ABS and PFS surveys, as well as to compare the findings about select core attributes measured in 2022 with corresponding findings from the 2009 NHTS and the 2017 NHTS. To carry out this goal, the team used the results of analyses that were carried out and their

professional judgments to advance reasoning tying the identified differences in design features to the observed differences in core attributes.

2.5 Analytical Considerations

All of the analyses of household-related attributes for the ABS survey in this evaluation were performed using the final household weights made available to the evaluation team; however, these weights were untrimmed instead of trimmed (future releases of the data will reportedly include the trimmed weights). Although the trimming would impact only a small percentage of the total number of cases (1.2%), this caveat must be kept in mind for any conclusions reached in the evaluation, as the impact of large weights can vary substantially across different outcomes of interest.

2.5.1 Core Attributes

Table 1 lists the core attributes for the 2022 NHTS surveys. FHWA chose these attributes and designed the surveys to seek to ensure their statistical reliability. The attributes include demographic characteristics and travel-related metrics at the household, person, and trip levels.

Table 1: Core Attributes for the 2022 NHTS Surveys

<i>Level</i>	<i>Core Attribute</i>
Household	Household Size
	Vehicle Count
	Race of Reference Person
	Hispanic Origin of Reference Person
	Household Income
Person	Age
	Sex
	Employment Status
	Education Level
	Online Purchase Deliveries
	Reason for Fewer Trips
	Typical Taxi Usage
	Typical Transportation Network Company (TNC) Usage
	Usage of New Transportation Services
	Trip Parking Cost
	Work From Home
	Work From Home Frequency
Usual Mode to Work	
Vehicle	Trip Start of Driver-Driven Trips
	Trip End for Driver-Driven Trips
	Duration for Driver-Driven Trips
	Distance for Driver-Driven Trips
	Vehicle Type
	Trip Purpose for Driver-Driven Trips
	Travel Party Size for Driver-Driven Trips

2.5.2 Statistical Methods

Given the evaluation’s purpose to identify nonignorable/meaningful differences between the 2022 NHTS ABS and PFS data, the vast majority of statistical comparisons tested by the evaluation team involved only the two 2022 survey datasets.

Tabular summaries of survey results were produced containing parameter estimate, corresponding confidence interval, and p-value for the difference between ABS and PFS results. Initial weights and strata were used for 2022 ABS and PFS datasets. All analytic results for core attribute sample

percentages were created with SAS procedure SURVEYMEANS. Percentage estimates and their related standard errors were compared using z-tests to provide initial p values.

Results for 2022 ABS and PFS surveys were produced using the SAS macro “Table”, which was written for use with the 1995 NHTS. This macro was designed to enable calculation of estimates and associated standard errors in SAS for cases where Taylor Series approximation was used to generate the survey weights. Outcome estimates and their related standard errors were compared using z-tests to provide initial p-values. SAS procedure SURVEYFREQ was used to provide Chi-square results for overall differences.

Hundreds of comparisons between ABS and PFS survey results occurred as part of the evaluation. These comparisons include comparisons of core attributes and other travel metrics from the ABS and PFS surveys, as well as comparisons of demographics in both datasets against other sources of data (e.g., Census, American Community Survey [ACS]). The former comparisons were undertaken to evaluate whether there were any statistically significant differences between the results obtained from each survey. The latter comparisons were undertaken to identify potential reasons (e.g., noncoverage errors) for any differences found. For these comparisons, the evaluation team used t-tests, z-tests, Chi-square, and correlation tests, depending on the particular comparison.

Because of the sheer number of comparisons made in the evaluation, consideration needed to be made concerning the possibility of incorrectly identifying a result as statistically significant (i.e., a Type I error false positive). To minimize the likelihood of this situation, the evaluation team used the Bonferroni-Holm method to conservatively adjust p-values for the multiple simultaneous comparisons by controlling the familywise error rate (Holm, 1979). This method was run separately for the comparisons of ABS and PFS survey results and the evaluations of data collection procedures (e.g., attrition rates, item nonresponse). In both cases, the method was first run using a familywise error rate of 0.05 and then a second time using a rate of 0.10 to identify statistically significant comparisons for the core attributes. The more-conservative and less-conservative thresholds were run so that a determination could be made regarding which one to use. In the end, only five ABS-vs-PFS comparisons were statistically significant at the 0.10 rate but not at the 0.05 rate. Similarly, there were only three comparisons that differed between the two rates for the evaluations of data collection procedures.

Statistical analysis was performed using SAS (version 9.4) on the 64-bit platform.

In discussions with the FHWA, it was determined that “nonignorable/meaningful results” (i.e., nonignorable, thus meaningful differences between the two 2022 NHTS survey findings for an attribute being measured) would be defined as meeting the $p < .05$ threshold and that the paired findings that were being compared for the two 2022 surveys would need to differ from each other by at least five percent (i.e., not five percentage points) in absolute value.

3. Results

This section presents the core attributes that were found to differ at a meaningful statistically significant degree between the two surveys, the methodological and statistical differences that we discovered between the two surveys designs as implemented, organized by the key sources of potential error that the TSE framework identifies, and how they may explain the nonignorable differences in the core attributes as measured via the two 2022 surveys.

3.1 Nonignorable Difference in Core Attributes between the Two Surveys

As shown in Table 2, there were very few differences in core attributes between the two surveys.

Table 2: Meaningfully Statistically Significant Differences in Core Attributes Between Surveys

Core Attribute	Response	Estimate [percentage] (95% Confidence Interval)		ABS vs. PFS p-value	Percentage Difference (ABS vs PFS)#
		2022 ABS	2022 PFS		
Race of Reference Person	Asian	7.08 (6.16, 7.99)	3.80 (3.34, 4.25)	<0.0001+	46.34%*
Race of Reference Person	White	73.52 (71.89, 75.15)	80.70 (79.74, 81.66)	<0.0001+	-9.76%*
Hispanic Origin of Reference Person	Hispanic or Latino	14.48 (13.02, 15.95)	10.96 (10.18, 11.73)	<0.0001+	24.35%*
Online purchase deliveries	11+ Deliveries	13.79 (12.79, 14.79)	9.59 (8.97, 10.21)	<0.0001+	30.45%*
Typical TNC usage – Used rideshare in last 30 days	Yes	17.25 (16.00, 18.49)	11.27 (10.54, 11.99)	<0.0001+	34.67%*
Typical TNC usage – Used rideshare in last 30 days	No	82.21 (80.95, 83.47)	88.09 (87.34, 88.84)	<0.0001+	-7.16%*
Usage of new transportation services – EScooter	Yes	1.90 (1.51, 2.29)	0.90 (0.69, 1.10)	<0.0001+	52.76%*

- Only households that completed the survey via CAWI are included.

Calculated as $100 * (ABS - PFS) / ABS$

+ Statistically significant at the 0.05 level (with Bonferroni-Holm adjustment)

* Meaningfully statistically significant (percentage difference $> \pm 5\%$)

3.2 Coverage Issues and Possible Coverage Errors

Using data at the Zip Code Tabulation Area (ZCTA) level for Census and ACS variables, it was found that the initial sample for the 2022 NHTS PFS covered (i.e., represented) the NHTS’s target population more closely than did the initial sample of the 2022 NHTS ABS. This could be due to two factors that were not able to be disentangled.

First, the respective frames used for the two surveys might cover the target population differently, with the PFS frame covering it more accurately than the ABS frame. Because there was no direct access to the frames for both 2022 NHTS surveys, this factor could not be investigated. However, the evaluation team reasoned that this factor seems unlikely to be the explanation in light of the long experience and high reputation of the sampling vendor that created the ABS frame.

Second, the evaluation team suspected that a plausible explanation for these differences may lie in the underlying differences in sampling designs across the two studies that were used to generate the respective samples. In particular, the ABS initial sample design contained fewer parameters (i.e., stratification variables) compared to the number of variables that were used to govern the selection of the PFS sample (i.e., variables used to create the size variable used in the PFS PPS sampling design). Therefore, had the ABS initial sample been stratified using the same variables that were used to create the size measures governing selection of the PFS initial sample, the evaluation team reasoned that it is less likely that the observed differences in coverage between the two 2022 NHTS surveys would have occurred. Thus, the respective deviations of the ABS initial sample from the NHTS population parameters may not have been as large as they were.

3.3 Sampling Design Issues and Possible Sampling Errors

Differential fielding of the two surveys resulted in a different pattern of completed cases for the ABS survey compared to those from the PFS survey, with more ABS completed cases (see plotted red circles in Figure 2) in the early part of the field period (winter and early spring months) and fewer completes in late spring and summer months followed by higher levels of completes in the fall months. This pattern contrasts to the nearly uniform pattern of completes for the PFS survey (see plotted blue asterisks in Figure 2) across the entire field period (Note. Day 1 is January 20, 2022). The evaluation team also examined the patterns of completes for the 18 strata and found fairly consistent patterns to those depicted in Figure 2 across both rural and urban areas within a majority of the Census divisions.

Figure 2: Number of Completed Cases per Day over the Survey Field Period by Survey Type

Not surprisingly, the degree of sampling error that was observed for each survey was more substantial for the ABS survey in comparison to the PFS survey, in part due to limited stratification variables that may grossly be associated with some, but not all, travel outcomes and more substantial per-month adjustments that were needed in response to the adaptive recruitment strategy used for the ABS survey, which was constrained by the finite budget available for recruitment in the two 2022 surveys.

3.4 Unit Nonresponse Issues and Possible Nonresponse Errors

Using ZCTA-level data, it was found that some of the responding subsamples in the 2022 NHTS ABS and PFS surveys differed in meaningfully statistically significant ways from their respective nonresponding counterparts. In each survey, the correlates of response/nonresponse were very similar.

In the judgment of the evaluation team, it is likely that differential nonresponse within the two 2022 NHTS surveys led to some of the observed differences in the core travel attributes that are present. However, it is not possible to create a confident quantitative estimate of the sizes and natures of the effects with the available data. Nevertheless, it was found (see Table 3) that where there were nonignorable differences between the two surveys, in almost all cases the PFS responding subsample was closer to the NHTS population parameters than was the ABS responding subsample.

Table 3: Response Differences among Core and Other Attributes by Survey

<i>Attribute[^]</i>	<i>2020 Census / Most Recent ACS</i>	<i>ABS Initial Sample Completes</i>	<i>PFS Initial Sample Completes</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Percentage Difference#</i>
Pct. Urban	83.46%	83.39%	84.60%	0.0407	-1.45%
Pct. Census South	38.16%	36.91%	37.31%	0.6083	-1.08%
Pct. Female	50.76%	50.80%	50.83%	0.4964	-0.06%
Pct. Age 20 to 34	13.36%	13.03%	13.04%	0.9748	-0.03%
Pct. Age 65+	16.03%	16.88%	16.70%	0.0912	1.09%
Pct. Black/African American	12.62%	10.35%	11.91%	<0.0001+	-15.05%*
Pct. White	70.42%	74.96%	72.46%	<0.0001+	3.34%
Pct. Hispanics	18.18%	13.93%	16.18%	<0.0001+	-16.15%*
Pct. Spanish	12.43%	9.05%	10.85%	<0.0001+	-19.93%*
Pct. Foreign Born	13.51%	11.40%	12.47%	<0.0001+	-9.41%*
Pct. English Spoken Only	73.85%	77.92%	75.99%	<0.0001+	2.47%
Pct. Less Than 9th Grade	5.06%	3.79%	4.36%	<0.0001+	-14.92%*
Pct. Some High School	6.66%	5.66%	6.13%	<0.0001+	-8.31%*
Pct. Bachelor's Degree or More	32.61%	36.27%	34.55%	<0.0001+	4.74%
Median Household Income	\$70,552	\$73,609	\$71,788	0.0001+	2.47%
Pct. Poverty	12.94%	11.71%	12.37%	<0.0001+	-5.65%*
Pct. Single Mothers	6.53%	5.85%	6.22%	<0.0001+	-6.28%*
Pct. Owner Occupied	64.55%	65.92%	65.08%	0.0023	1.28%
Pct. Units 20+	8.88%	9.29%	9.33%	0.8721	-0.38%
Pct. Mobile Homes	5.76%	5.22%	5.43%	0.1052	-3.99%
Pct. Vacant Units	9.97%	10.05%	9.97%	0.5762	0.76%
Pct. Number of Vehicles	8.18%	7.63%	8.00%	0.0206	-4.92%
Pct. No Internet	7.94%	7.15%	7.55%	<0.0001+	-5.50%*
Census Response Score - Internet	40.91%	43.34%	42.67%	0.0382	1.53%
Census Response Score - Traditional	10.38%	9.87%	10.23%	0.0034	-3.57%
Census Response Score - All	51.29%	53.21%	52.90%	0.3707	0.58%

Calculated as $100 * (ABS - PFS) / ABS$

* Meaningfully statistically significant (percentage difference > ±5%)

+ Statistically significant at the 0.05 level (with Bonferroni-Holm adjustment)

So, at this level, there is evidence that the differential cross-survey differences between the nonresponse, and likely nonresponse biases, in each survey may help to explain the relatively small number of core attributes that were shown to differ at a nonignorable level between the two 2022 NHTS surveys. And, because of this, it is reasoned that the PFS measures may have less nonresponse bias associated with them than do the ABS measures.

3.5 Adjustment/Weighting Issues and Possible Adjustment Errors

The sampling designs for the 2022 NHTS ABS and PFS surveys were different in a few marked ways that affected how the weighting for the household, person, and trip was performed. Generally speaking, the household weighting for both surveys computed a “base weight” that reflected either the initial selection probability or a proxy of it (in the case of the PFS), and then made subsequent adjustments to these base weights for day of travel completion, stratum size by month, and overall adjustments for the month and day of travel completion to form design weights. The design weights were further adjusted to population benchmarks for variables found to be related to nonresponse in each of the respective surveys. The evaluation of survey nonresponse was done separately by survey and as a result, the variables used in the final raking/calibration of the design weights differed across the two surveys. Household-specific variables were more common among the list of factors used to calibrate the PFS survey, while householder-specific variables were more common for calibrating the ABS survey.

Per the survey contractor’s documentation, an interquartile rule was applied to trim weights that were excessively large in an attempt to balance variance and bias of resulting estimates for both 2022 NHTS surveys. In particular, weights that exceeded the upper quartile by more than three times the IQR or were less than the first quartile by more than three times the IQR were reportedly trimmed back to these limits.

However, upon inspection of the distribution of the household weights for the ABS survey, the evaluation team discovered that the weights available in the advance-release datasets provided for evaluation were in fact not the trimmed weights, but rather the calibrated household weights. As such, the evaluation team was not able to establish the impact of trimming on the ABS survey, since the trimmed versions of the weights were not available in time for the completion of the evaluation. The distribution of the calibrated weights indicated that there were several candidates for trimming in the ABS survey, as displayed by the longer tail of the distribution depicted in the bottom (red) curve in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Distribution of Final Household Weights for the PFS and ABS Surveys that were Available

According to the documentation made available to the evaluation team, there was no mention of trimming any of the household weights for the PFS survey. The distribution of the final weights for the PFS survey is illustrated in the top (blue) curve of Figure 3. One thing to note here is that the

PFS weights are more constrained with a much lighter right tail in the distribution, indicating far fewer large weights when compared to the heavier right tail of the household weights from the ABS survey.

The person weights for both surveys were computed by calibrating the respective final, trimmed household weights to person-level control totals. The same interquartile rule was applied to the person weights to determine whether any of the person weights were to be trimmed. For the 2022 ABS survey, the documentation reported that no person weights needed to be trimmed, while approximately 3% of the PFS person weights were trimmed. The distribution of the final person weights is provided in Figure 4, with ABS weights shown in the bottom (red) curve and PFS weights shown in the top (blue) curve.

Figure 4: Distribution of the Final Person Weights for the 2022 NHTS PFS and ABS Surveys as were Available

From examining these distributions and considering the trimming rules documented in the contractor’s weighting memo, one would conclude that trimming should have been applied to the ABS person weights, but they were not. These larger-than-expected person weights likely had an impact on point estimates and resulting standard errors for person-related variables for the ABS survey compared to those derived from the PFS survey. Because trip weights are a scalar function of the person weights, omissions in trimming person weights result in similarly large number of trip weights that could also impact estimates of travel-related outcomes.

3.6 Respondent-related Measurement Issues and Possible Measurement Errors

Each of the two 2022 NHTS surveys used the same CAWI questionnaire. For the PFS completions, 100% of the data were provided via the CAWI questionnaire. For the ABS completions more than 99% of the completions were provided via CAWI, with less than 1% coming in via respondent-requested hard-copy mailback (aka PAPI) questionnaires.

Although it was found that the ABS subsample returning a PAPI questionnaire provided meaningfully statistically significantly different data than their ABS CAWI counterparts on some core attributes, the evaluation team reasoned that it is most likely that those differences are associated with the markedly different demographic profile of the ABS PAPI respondents versus the profile of the ABS CAWI respondents. Of course, no such differences exist in the PFS data, as only the CAWI mode was used for their data collection.

It also was reasoned that the proportion of completions in the ABS sample made up by PAPI respondents was far too small (< 1%) to explain the observed meaningfully statistically significant differences in core attributes between the ABS completions and the PFS completions.

However, there was another potentially serious measurement difference between the two 2022 NHTS surveys, and it may have created differential measurement errors, in the PFS survey but not in the ABS survey. That is the problem that the survey measurement error literature shows can be caused by the panel conditioning (aka “time-in-the-panel”) of panelists. Some past research on panels has shown that panel conditioning effects can have deleterious impacts on panel data quality (i.e., on their reliability and construct validity), while in other past research studies, possible positive effects of panel conditioning have been hypothesized and evidence has been provided to support those findings (cf. Struminskaya, B., & Bosnjak, M., 2021). However, this evaluation was not designed or funded to investigate panel conditioning effects in the 2022 NHTS PFS survey. In contrast, the 2022 NHTS ABS data were gathered in a one-time cross-sectional survey and thus there would be no possibility of panel conditioning effects in that 2022 NHTS survey.

Furthermore, it is reasoned that there are likely to be other types of measurement errors in each of the 2022 NHTS surveys (e.g., ones associated with straight-lining, acquiesce bias, extreme-response choice bias, primacy bias) that were not investigated in this evaluation, because such an investigation was neither requested nor funded.

In conclusion, it is not possible to state with confidence whether some nonignorable measurement error differences contributed to the observed differences in the measurement of some of the core attributes by the two 2022 surveys.

4. Discussion

4.1 Summary of the Evaluation’s TSE-related Findings

In trying to understand possible causes of the meaningfully statistically significant differences between the two 2022 NHTS surveys, a rigorous TSE investigation of the different methods and statistics associated with the two surveys was carried out.

Evidence was found in this investigation to suggest that:

- The coverage of the NHTS’ target population by the ABS survey was less robust than by the PFS survey, suggesting that noncoverage may have biased some of the ABS-measured core attributes.
- The sampling approach for the PFS survey was more constrained than that of the ABS sampling design in that it used geography plus other household variables related to travel outcomes to create the size measures used in the PPS sampling approach used to select the PFS sample.
- The initial sample drawn from the ABS sampling frame appeared to yield a less representative initial ABS sample of the target population than did the PFS initial sample that resulted from the sampling of the PFS frame.
- Nonresponse in both the ABS and PFS surveys was mostly associated with lower-socioeconomic-status (SES) addresses/panelists in the two surveys’ final samples of respondents that completed the NHTS questionnaire process.
 - Because lower-SES households have different patterns of travel than higher-SES households, this logically suggests that some of the final 2022 NHTS data in both surveys were biased in their measurement of travel-related attributes.
- In terms of differential response/nonresponse between the two surveys, the PFS survey’s final sample characteristics (race, education, other SES-related) were closer to the NHTS population parameters than were the ABS survey’s characteristics for its final sample.
- Determining whether the nonresponse in both surveys was associated with nonresponse bias in the surveys was not possible; that is, although there were nonresponse investigations

- carried out (per Office of Management and Budget guidelines) by the survey contractor, no investigation into possible nonresponse biases was carried out.
- While design weights were computed similarly across the two surveys, the trimming protocols did not seem to be equally applied across the two surveys. PFS person weights were trimmed even though a smaller percentage of extreme weights were identified compared to the ABS person weights which were deemed to not require trimming. This led to excessively large person (and consequently trip) weights for the ABS survey.
 - Differences in mailing and replicate releases across the two surveys resulted in differential adjustments by month that created relatively uniformly distributed PFS weights over the year of the field period but created higher household and person weights in the spring and summer months for the ABS survey.
 - The usage of panelists as respondents in the PFS survey may be associated with a form of respondent-related measurement error, termed “panel conditioning” (possible deleterious effects that affect the data quality among some panelists), especially long-term ones—aka “time in panel” effects. However, this remains uncertain as it was not possible to investigate the presence of panel conditioning in the survey contractor’s panel. These possible effects do not apply to a cross-sectional (one-time) ABS survey.

All in all, the major conclusions that were reached in this comparative evaluation of the two 2022 NHTS surveys were:

- The two surveys did not differ to a meaningful extent in terms of point estimates derived for several core travel attributes.
- While the point estimates from both surveys were generally consistent, the width of the resulting confidence intervals around those estimates were more often wider (i.e., less precise) for the ABS survey compared to the PFS survey. Specifically, for 497 of 599 (83%) variables considered, the confidence interval for the ABS estimate was wider than that for the corresponding PFS estimate. Half of the ABS intervals were at least 32% wider than those from the PFS and about 25% of them were at least 46% wider. If policy makers want to use interval estimates rather than point estimates to consider worst- and best-case scenarios (i.e. lower and upper endpoints of the confidence interval, respectively), the PFS interval estimates give the appearance of being more accurate compared to the ABS, but this accuracy or lack thereof for the ABS survey is likely a result of the constrained sampling and weighting process used for the PFS survey and lack of trimming extreme weights in the ABS survey.
- Each of the two surveys likely underrepresented the travel attributes of lower-SES households.
- Had more funding been available, more could have been done by the survey contractor to address coverage issues and possible errors, nonresponse issues and possible errors, and respondent-related measurement issues and possible errors, as well as the weighting of each 2022 NHTS survey, which in turn would likely have improved the accuracy of each survey, but likely to a differential extent.

4.2 To what Extent were the 2022 NHTS Studies Fit for Purpose (FfP)?

In addition to the accuracy of a survey there are several other criteria by which a survey can be evaluated to determine the extent to which it is “fit for purpose” (FfP) by using a Total Quality Framework (cf. Biemer and Lyberg, 2003). The Director of the U.S. Census Bureau at the time this manuscript was published, Dr. Robert Santos, has described a Fit for Purpose assessment of a survey as follows: “the balance [that] researchers seek between available resources, the rigor of [the] research design and [its] implementation, and the nature of the insights needed to effectively address the research questions” (Santos, 2014, p. 773).

The criteria that are used to assess whether a survey is FfP are: Timeliness, Accessibility, Relevance, Interpretability, Accuracy, and Coherence (Dever et al, 2021).

What follows are judgements based on the professional expertise of the evaluation team members with survey research methods and statistics while considering all they learned during this evaluation. This assessment of FfP applies to both the 2022 NHTS ABS and 2022 NHTS PFS surveys.

4.2.1 Timeliness

The 2022 NHTS surveys and associated deliverables were completed within the timeframes that were set for them.

4.2.2 Accessibility

The 2022 NHTS surveys gathered the data that were required, and via means that were, for the most part, appropriate to meet the Federal government's needs.

4.2.3 Relevance

The 2022 NHTS data that were needed for the analyses to be carried out were mostly sufficient for those needs, although the adequacy of the weighting of the data is unclear, as noted elsewhere in this manuscript.

4.2.4 Interoperability

The survey design, collected data, and subsequent computed estimates were, with few exceptions, sufficient for the particular needs of the 2022 NHTS surveys.

4.2.5 Accuracy

As noted throughout this manuscript, for the most part, the 2022 NHTS data and resulting estimates were in line with the intended target population of the surveys and reasonably within acceptable levels of TSE (precision and bias). Concerns about accuracy were associated with possible coverage errors, sampling errors (e.g., wider confidence interval estimates), nonresponse errors (inadequate response from lower-SES households and persons), adjustment errors, and measurement errors.

4.2.6 Coherence

Overall, the resulting estimates are in line with other sources of information on the constructs measured by the 2022 NHTS questionnaire, once the effects of the Covid pandemic are taken into account.

4.2.7 Conclusion

All in all, it is reasonable to conclude that the two 2022 NHTS surveys were generally FfP.

Addendum

Our 2024 AAPOR conference presentation and this paper are condensed versions of a detailed report, Statistical Assessment of Data Collection Efforts for the 2022 NextGen National Household Travel Survey: Final Evaluation Report, prepared and submitted by the Battelle Memorial Institute to the Office of Highway Policy Information of the Federal Highway Administration. FHWA Contract Number: 693JJ319D000006, Task Order: 693JJ319F000289.

References

- Biemer, P. P. (2010). Total survey error: Design, implementation, and evaluation. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 74(5), 817–848.
- Biemer, P., and Lyberg, L. (2003). *Introduction to Survey Quality*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- Dever, J.A., Amaya, A., Srivastav, A., Roycroft, J., Stanley, M., Stringer, M.C., Bostwick, M.G., Greby, S.M., Santibanez, T.A., and Williams, W.W. (2021). *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*, 9(3), pp. 449–476.

- Groves, R. M. (1989). *Survey Errors and Survey Costs*. John Wiley and Sons: New York, New York.
- Groves, R.M., Fowler, F.J., Couper, M., Lepkowski, J., Singer, E., and Tourangeau, R. (2009). *Survey Methodology*. (2nd Ed.) Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- Lavrakas, P. J. (2013). Applying a 'Total Error' Perspective to All Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods. Presentation at the 2013 International Total Survey Error Workshop. Ames, Iowa.
- Santos, R. (2014). Presidential Address: Borne of a Renaissance—A Metamorphosis for Our Future *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 78(3), pp. 769–777.
- Struminskaya, B., & Bosnjak, M., (2021). Panel conditioning: Types, causes and empirical evidence of what we know so far. In: *Advances in Longitudinal Survey Methodology*. Ed. by P. Lynn, John Wiley and Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey.